

PRINCIPLES OF USE “了”

Tojiboyev Islom Odil o'g'li

Student of Samarkand state Institute of foreign languages

Phone number: +998997777210

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we will look at similar grammatical rules for the use of “了”, as well as their use with adjectives, and the fact that “了” is formed over time, and that “了” is used not only to be le but also to succeed.

The suffix “了” is very common in Chinese, so it is important to understand its meaning in order to understand the meaning in general. In this article, we distinguish each use of the suffix “了”, thus providing an overview of the use of this suffix in Chinese and the rules of their use.

In other words, the suffix “了”:

- Confirmation of qualities in Russian and Uzbek languages;
- Indicating a change in circumstances;
- To indicate that the action is over;
- And sometimes there is no “了” at all.

The most common use of “了” in Chinese is to reinforce the qualities - it serves to strengthen the qualities emotionally.

- To enhance practice;
- Report a change of situation;

- To indicate that the action is complete.

As mentioned above, the Chinese suffix “了” can be used to describe the emotional aspects of adjectives in such examples;

Adj (words) 了

(adj.) 极了

(adj.) 死了

Adj (words) 了

All such words are used to exaggerate adjectives, each of which must use the suffix 了. In this case, the structure 太 (adj.) 了 is also used to denote an excess of something, and the structure (adj.) 极了 is used only with positive adjectives, (adj.) 死了 usually has a negative meaning.

Here we can see that there are some examples of the emotional enhancement of qualities by the particle 了;

- 太棒了!

Tài bàng le!

Great! / Great!

- 这个盒子太大了。

Zhège hézi tài dà le.

This box is too big.

- 你的汉语好极了。

Nǐ de hànǔ hǎo jí le.

Your Chinese is so good!

- 饿死了!

È sǐ le

We are so hungry; we have no energy!

If we pay attention to this, "了" does not mean anything here. If we use it in the past tense, we will see that "了" has a place in it. Examples of this are the following.

- 昨天我感冒了

Yesterday I had a cold.

- 他上班迟到了

He was late for work.

Also, to complete the "了" action, we often see how the suffix "了" is placed after the verb. This is another way to use it - it means the action is over. It should be noted that this verb has nothing to do with the tense - the action can be performed in the past, present or future.

- 我偷了三辆车。

Zuótiān wǒ tōu le sān liàng chē.

I stole three cars yesterday.

- 到了城里卖掉卖掉我偷的车。

Wǒ dào le chéng lǐ mài diào wǒ tōu de chē.

I came to the city to sell stolen cars.

This is what happens when different aspects of grammar come together. For example, a sentence can immediately express both the completeness of the action and the change in the situation. In this case, two suffixes are used "了" and in many sentences the suffix 已经 (yǐjīng) is "already". It always happens - for example, let's talk about what happened so far:

- 他已经吃了八八碗面条了!

Tā yǐjīng chī le bā wǎn miàntiáo le!

She has already eaten eight bowls of noodles!

他们已经跑了两个两个小时步了。

Tāmen yǐjīng pǎo le liǎng gè xiǎoshí bù le.

They ran for two hours.

The Chinese suffix "了" has another meaning, but this time it is not like le, but an object that comes after the verb to describe the action in more detail. Liǎo is used to indicate whether an action expressed by a verb is successful or not. In addition, the appendix indicates whether this action is possible. For this purpose, it is combined with "了" (liǎo), 得 de ("possible") or 不 bù ("impossible"). Thus, it means that an action can be performed, but on the contrary, it means that an action is impossible.

- 我做得了。

Wo zuò dé liǎo.

I can do it.

The last grammatically correct syllable of "了" corresponds to the present continuous tense, the Present Continuous Tense. In this case, "了" is hesitant. That is:

- 我们写了这个作文半点了。

We have been writing this essay for half an hour.

- 他们听了音乐一点半了。

They have been listening to music for an hour and a half.

We can see from this that the suffix "了" in the Chinese language appears in several places, and the principles of their use remain, and we have tried to explain it with examples. From this it can be seen that the suffix "了" is made in several places on the basis of these grammatical rules.

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